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Review Article

Tradition to Translational Science: A Review of Modern Applications of Ayurvedic Formulations in Skin Care

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ABSTRACT

Ayurvedic cosmeceuticals dates back to the Indus valley civilization and is being used in human society from ancient time. It is now gaining importance in the beautification and to cure the skin ailments. In last 3-4 decades the use of cosmetics has increased exponentially not only among female but also in male population and play an important role in the FMCG sector. In the ancient classical texts of Ayurveda there are several references of numerous medicinal plants and mode of applications of their processed formulation for enhancing complexion, treating acne, treating dark patches, curing boils and carbuncles, etc. Consideration in this field can be helpful in making the herbs more acceptable, precious, life saving and economy promoter for the mankind. This review made a humble effort to make a monograph of ayurvedic plants that were mentioned by ayurvedic luminaries in the field of skincare.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics are considered to be one of the essential commodities of life. It is the fulcrum of First moving consumer's good (FMCG) sector. The cosmetics in general are external preparation and are meant to be applied to external part of the body. In other word they may be applied to skin, hair and nail for the purpose of beautification, protection or to cure the diseases of the exposed surface of the body¹. Ayurveda is one of the most ancient medical traditions practiced in India and other

South Asian countries. The total number of plants mentioned in Ayurveda are 1773, however the main classics of Ayurveda viz. Charak Samhita, Sushruta Samhita and Astang Sangrah (Brihat Trayee) have detailed descriptions of about 700 herbs². Several herbs have been mentioned in Ayurveda which can be used to obtain healthy skin and glowing complexion. Ayurvedic literature describes over 200 herbs, number of minerals and fats to maintain and enhance the health and beauty of the skin. Today there is once again a revival of preference for natural products, and in recent years there has been a great upsurge in the study of

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Indian herbs³. Ayurvedic cosmetics are in use and practice since thousands of year in India, without any side effect and are well proven and documented. The analysis of many herbal ingredient using modern scientific technologies has led to the identification of phytochemical components in Indian herbs, which deliver functional benefits anti dandruff, deodorant, age-defying properties etc.

Pre-formulation studies are not only important for medicinal preparations but also for cosmetics. Currently, pre-formulation studies related to cosmetic preparations, especially skin cosmetics,

have not been widely compared to studies on drug preformulation. So far, no pre-formulation reviews discussing cosmetics have been published. The design of an appropriate skin cosmetics preparation requires pre-formulation studies to consider the physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the materials that will be used to make cosmetic products. With the review regarding the pre-formulation study on skin cosmetics preparations, readers will find it easier to obtain various information related to cosmetic pre-formulation and get a better understanding of the various studies that have been reviewed.

This review examines various aspects of cosmetic pre-formulation so that it is expected to be able to provide benefits as a consideration in preformulating specifically on cosmetics, thereby capable of producing optimal cosmetics and providing a thorough understanding. The desire to always look attractive has become a trend in today's society. Through an attractive appearance, someone may increase self-confidence. Cosmetics are chosen to support one's performance. However, in reality there are many cosmetic products that can actually endanger the users. Studies showed that the hazardous material in cosmetics may lead to cases of breast cancer (Cardoso et al., 2016).

On a mild scale, allergies caused by the use of harmful cosmetics irritate the skin of the user (Khan and Alam, 2019). Therefore, screening the ingredients of cosmetic products before use is an important step. This work is expected to become a basis for producers in making cosmetics to determine what aspects that need attention. Pre-formulation studies can be carried out before the cosmetic manufacturing process to ensure the feasibility of a safe product for long-term use. 1.1 Cosmetics Recently, cosmetics have been a necessity for men and women. The need for cosmetics is often associated with the assumption relating to physical attractiveness. In general, cosmetics are ingredients used to adorn the face area such as cheeks, lips, even the eyes. They

contain many chemical ingredients that can skin contact, enter the body through inhalation, or, for lipsticks, accidentally swallowed (Park et al., 2015).

Daily use of cosmetics may lead to a local skin problem, which is a systemic effect from the absorption of those chemical ingredients into the skin (Mesko et al., 2020). The need for cosmetics in all kinds of people resulted in cosmetic manufacturers compete to gain a place in the market. However, many manufacturers produce cosmetics not up to standard. Continuous use of harmful cosmetics can jeopardize health. the skin (Mesko et al., 2020). The need for cosmetics in all kinds of people resulted in cosmetic manufacturers compete to gain a place in the market. However, many manufacturers produce cosmetics not up to standard. Continuous use of harmful cosmetics can jeopardize health.

Preparation of Topical Cosmetics If used as a cleanser, to beautify the skin or hair seen from the perspective of esthetics, then preparation is called cosmetics. However, if the objective is not only to beautify, but also affect the body therapeutically, then it is considered a drug. The FDA (Food Drug Administration) has explained that cosmetics are different than drugs. A drug is a substance, or a combination of substances, intended for the diagnosis, alleviate, cure or prevent a disease or to affect the function of the body.

Meanwhile, cosmetic is a substance, or a combination of substances, used smeared, poured, dipped, sprayed, or inserted into or on the body to clean, beautify, increase attractiveness, or improve the appearance without affecting the structure or function of the body (Turnbull, 2018). The topical formulation is aimed to target skin uses in various cosmetics, protection, and therapeutical use (Hadgraft and Lane, 2016).

Most cosmetic preparations are formulated through emulsification. However, this method is thermodynamically unstable. Polymers, carbomers or fatty alcohol are added to the cosmetic to stabilize the preparation. Any damage to the preparation can change the composition of the cosmetics and cause health problems and reduce product appeal. The use of preservative and antimicrobial agents can be an alternative to cope with this problem. Although many preservatives work on the microbial cell membrane, the mechanism can affect the stability of the cosmetic, thus the addition of preservatives should be considered (Hayase, 2017).

Anatomy of the Human Skin

is an organ with important functions to the body, including protection, thermoregulation, and immune response. The cross-section of human skin anatomy can be seen in Figure 1. The outer skin layer is an epidermis, a tissue that continuously undergoes regeneration. Epidermal regeneration occurs because the epidermis does not contain vascularization, thus no nutrition to maintain tissue survivability. There are five layers of the epidermis. The order from the outer layer to the inner layer is the stratum corneum, stratum lucidum, stratum granulosum, stratum spinosum, and germinative or basal layer (Karadzovska et al., 2013; Mathes et al., 2014; Notman and Anwar, 2013). The cells in the stratum corneum are known as corneocytes.

These cells are solid, functionally dead, nucleated, and filled with keratin. The composition of the stratum corneum is analogous to the wall of “brick and mortar”. The inner structure, the lipid cells in between are like mortars and corneocytes are like bricks. Lipid forms several bilayers arranged surrounding the corneocytes. Between lipid, cells lie a combination of cholesterol, ceramide, fatty acid, cholesteryl ester, and a small amount of

cholesterol sulfate (Anissimov et al., 2013; Barry, 2001; El Maghraby et al., 2008; Hansen et al., 2013).

The stratum corneum is composed of 15 to 20 layers of corneocytes. In a dry state, it has a thickness of 10 to 15 μm . While hydrated, the stratum corneum swells and can reach 40 μm , which showed increased permeability. This provides a characteristic of barrier and resistance to water. The corneum layer is known as the main layer restricting the absorption of chemical substances through the skin (Anissimov et al., 2013; Cevc and Vierl, 2010; El Maghraby et al., 2008; Hansen et al., 2013). There is a study that the elevation of stratum corneum drastically increases skin permeability, while the elevation of all epidermis increases skin permeability to 1 to 2 times. Therefore, each layer of the skin affects permeability to a certain degree (Andrews et al., 2013).

Figure 2 describes the structure of the skin anatomy (the middle figure is a 3D structure of human skin episcopically). Hypodermis (white); reticular dermis (yellow); papillary dermis (blue); epidermis (pink). The scale bar represents 200 μm . Figure 2(a) Skin surface topography in a different part of the body. The form of different skin subunits. (i) the volar surface of the finger, (ii) back of the hand, (iii) stomach. Figure 2(b) (i) Illustration of the epidermis; formation of hexagonal-shaped corneocytes group from the basal epithelia replication. (ii) Cross-section through the human epidermis. Ceramide-rich epidermal layer looks clear above and the dermis looks white because of high collagen. Figure 2(c) (i) skin cross-section to the reticular dermis level. (ii) An episcopic image of the dermis showed intertwined orientation of collagen bers. The scale represents 200 μm . Figure 2(d) Flexible and loose microvacuolar collagen tissue. Figure 2(e)

Hypodermal fat image as seen through different images. (i) Hypodermal fat as seen from endoscopic surgery in living tissues that shows yellow lumps of fat. (ii) hypodermal fat as seen from excitation of two fluorescence

SKIN CARE

through Ayurveda According to Ayurveda healthy skin is a result of overall health condition of individuals and prescribes numerous skin care treatment that needs to be pursued at every stage of life. The function of ayurvedic herbs is to purify skin & eliminate vitiated Tridoshas (Vitiated Humor) from the body as they are mainly responsible for skin disorders & other diseases. Several herbs have been mentioned in Ayurveda which can be used to obtain healthy skin and glowing complexion. Specific measurement for the enhancement of different aspect of beauty and disease conditions in relation to skin are mentioned in ancient Ayurvedic texts, they are described in brief.

CHARAKA SAMHITA

In contest of skin disorder Charaka described about 18 type of kustha (obstinate skin disease including leprosy) which included vipadika (rhagdes), dadru (ringworm), pama (scabies) etc in Chikitsa Sthan and also in Nidan sthan⁵. Apart from this there are references of ten drug as Varnya (complexion promoting)- in Sutrasthan viz. Chandana (Santalum album), Punnaga (Calophyllum inophyllum), Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides), Useer (Vetiveria zizanioides), Madhuka (Glycyrrhiza glabra), Manjistha (Rubia cordifolia), Sariva (Hamidesmus indicus), Paysya (Ipomoea digitata), Sita (white variety of Cynodon dactylon), Lata (black variety of C.dactylon).

SUSHRUTA SAMHITA

In the Kshudra roga chikitsa (treatment of minor disease) many of the skin care treatments are documented.

Arumsika

(Eczema of face and scalp)- Blood should be let out and the lesion are washed with decoction of Nimba (*Azadirachta indica*) then applied paste of Hartal(Orpiment), Haldi (*Curcuma longa*), Patola patra (*Trichosanthes dioica* leaves), paste of Mulethi (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Nilotpala (*Nymphaea nouchali*), Erand (*Ricinus communis*) and Bhringaraj (*Eclipta alba*) paste. Vyanga (black spot), Nilika (Naevus) - puncturing of the vein is done in the forehead and rubbed roughly with Smudra Phena (Cuttle fish bone) and applied the paste of bark of kshira-vriksha (plant containing sap) or paste of Bala (*Sida cordifolia*), Atibala (*Abutilon indicum*) Yastimadhu (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Haldi (*Curcuma longa*) or of Arkpuspi (*Holostemma rheedie*), Aguru (*Aquilaria agallocha*), Kaliyaka (*Colchicium fenestratum*) and Gairika(Haematite). Yauvana Pidika (pimples/acne)- Applying the Paste of Vacha(*Acorus calamus*), Lodhra (*Symplocos racemosa*), Sendha (Rock-salt) and Sarso (*Brassica campestris*) or of paste of Dhanyaka(*Coriandrum sativum*), Vacha, Lodhra and Kuth (*Saussurea lappa*). Padadari (Rhagades)- Vein puncture should be done after fomentation and anointing, paste of Madhuchista (Bees wax), Vasa (fat), powder of Sarjika kshar (sodium salts), Yava kshar (potassium salts) and Gairika (Haematite) added with ghee and applied to the feet.

Astang Hridayam

There are three type of Mukhlepa (formulation applied on face) viz. for removal of dosha, for removal of poison and varnyakara(complexion promoting). Mode of application of paste over

face, duration and precaution were also elaborately mentioned. Furthermore application of paste varies according to the season.

Hemant

(Dewy season)-Paste of seed of Ber (*Ziziphus jujuba*), Vasaka root (*Adhatoda vasica*), Savara Lodhra (*Symplocos racemosa* or *paniculata*) Sarson (*Brassica campestris*) were applied.

Shisir

(Winter)-Kateri root (*Solanum surattense*), blacktil (*Sesamum indicum*),bark of Daruhaldi (*Berberis aristata*), Barly (*Hordeum vulgare*) without husk.

Basant

(Spring)-Paste of root of Dabh (*Imperata cylindrica*), Chandan (*Santalum album*), Khas (*Vetiveria zizanioidis*), Shiris (*Albizia lebbeck*), Saunf (*Foeniculum vulgare*), chawal (*Oriza sativa*).

Grisma

(Summer)- Kumud(*Nymphaea nouchali*), Utpal (*Nymphoea stellata*), Khas (*Vetiveria zizanioidis*), Durva (*Cynodon dactylon*), Yastimadhu (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Chandan (*Santlum album*).

Varsa

(Rainy season)- Kaliyaka (*Coscinium fenestratum*), Til (*Sesamum indicum*) khas (*Vetiveria zizanioidis*), Jatamansi (*Nordostachys Jatamansi*), Tagar (*Valeriana wallichii*), Padmk (*Nelumbo nucifera*).

Sarat

(Autumn)- Talis (*Abies webbiana*), Etkat (*Sesbania cannabina*), Pundarik (*Nelumbo*

nucifera), Muledi (Glycyrrhiza glabra), Khas (Vetiveria zizanioidis), Tagar (Vetiveria wallichii) and Agru (Aquilaria agallocha).

Vagbhatta mentioned the benefits of Mukhalepa as- **‘Mukhalepanashilanam dridam bhavati darshanam, Vadanam chaprimlanam shlakshanam tamrasopanam’**.(22/22) - which signifies that the persons who are habitual to application of paste of drug over face, the vision become keen, the face never dull and glows like lotus flower.

Astang Samgrah

Mukhadusika chikitsa (Acne)- In Mukhadusika, application of warm paste of Lodhra and Tuvarika (Hydnocarpus laurifolia) or leaves of Vata (Ficus bengalensis) and narikela shukti (coconut shell) or of Saindhava, Vacha, Aksibhesaja (Sabar lodhra - Symplocos racemosa or paniculata) and Sidharthaka (Brassica campestris) are prescribed.

Lancchana

(Patches on the face), vyanga (hyper pigmentation) and nilika (Naevus) chikitsa- In this group of diseases, the nearest vein should be cut and the area covered with the paste of bark of trees having milky sap or that of Bala (Sida cordifolia), Atibala (Abutilon indicum), Madhuka (Glycyrrhiza glabra) and Haridra or of Madhuka, Aguru, Payasya (Ipomoea digitata) and kaliyaka (Cosciniun fenestratum). Tender fruit of Kapittha (Feronia limonia), Tinduka (Diospyros peregrine) and Rajani (Curcuma longa), root of Amalika (Tamarindus indica) and Sukaradamstra (teeth of pig) are also added with honey and ghee.

Yogaratnakar

In kshudra rog (minor diseases), nidana chikitsa prakaran (chapter dealing with diagnosis and

prognosis) there are 44 types of minor diseases of which some are related to skin care.

Arumsika-

In Arumsika application of the paste of Nilkamal (Nymphaea stellata), Amlaki (Embllica officinalis), Yasthimadhu (Glycyrrhiza glabra) in equal amount are prescribed. Triphaladi tail and Haridradi tail are also prescribed. Triphaladi tail-Oil prepared by Triphala, Yasthimadhu, Bhringraj, Nilkamal, Sariva and Saindhav lavana are prescribed. Haridradi tail-Oil prepared by Haldi, Daruhaldi, Chiraita, Triphala bark of Nimbi and Rakta chandan are prescribed.

Vyanga

(dark patches on the face)- Tribhuvan, Bhangapatra (Cannabis sativa), Vidhara (Argyrea speciosa) and Sesam root (Dalbergia sissoo) or Masur (Lense culinaris) exhibit positive results in dark patches. Application of bark of Arjuna (Terminalia arjuna), Manjistha (Rubia cordifolia), and Adusa (Adhatoda vasica) in equal amount with butter shows good positive result in Vyanga.

Complexion promoting-

Masur (Lense culinaris) triturated with milk and applied with ghee for enhancing complexion. Kumkumadi tailam also prescribed for the promoting complexion.

Yauvana Pidika

(pimples/acne)- In pimples application of paste of Jaiphala (Myristica fragrans), Raktachandan (Pterocarpus santalinus), Maricha (Piper nigrum) or of Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa), Dhanyaka (Coriandrum sativum), Vacha (Acorus calamus) or of Safed sarso, Vacha, Lodhra and saindhava or of Semal (Salmalia malabarica) spine with milk.

Vipadika-

Application of paste of wax, saindhav, ghee, Guda(Jaggery) Guggulu (Commiphora weiti) ,gum of shal (Shorea robusta) and Geru (Haematite) or application of Madanadilepa prepared by Madanphala (Randia spinosa), Wax and Smudra lavana (Sea salt) shows positive result.

Saragadhar Samhita

There are three kinds of lepa viz. dosaghna (pacify the polluted humor), visaghna (pacify the poisonous substance) and varnya (cosmetic application for complexion).

Complexion promoting-Rakta chandana (Pterocarpus santalinus) Manjistha(Rubia cordifolia), Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa), kustha (Saussurea lappa), Priyangu (Callicarpa macrophylla) and Masura (Lense culinaris) have complexion promoting properties.

YauvanaPidika

(pimples/acne)- Ripened leaves of Vata (F. bengalensis), Malati, Rakta chandan (Pterocarpus santalinus), Kustha (Saussurea lappa), kaliyaka (Cosciniun fenestratum) and Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa) are made into paste and applied externally to remove pimples ,black spot and patches on the face.

Arumsika-

A paste of bark of Khadira (Acacia catechu), Aristha (Sapindus trifoliatus), Jambu (Syzygium cumini), Kutaj (Holarrhena antidysentrica) and Saindhav (rock salt) processed in cow's urine which cures arumsika.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

It is very clear from the above description that large number of herbs and other naturally obtained raw material have been formulated into cosmetics products and this pure natural cosmetics are without any synthetic chemical they are not only devoid of side effects but also equally effective in comparison to their modern counterparts. The use of bioactive ingredients in cosmetics influence biological functions of skin and provides nutrients necessary for the healthy skin. The vast array of knowledge of medicinal plants mentioned in ayurvedic texts is very helpful in the development of the new cosmetics products for present and future cosmeceuticals industry. The classical texts mentioned in the review are just the tip of the iceberg; apart from them there are several books in Ayurveda, which include broad descriptions about therapeutic effect of Ayurvedic plants in the field of skin care. There are several Nighantus (Lexicons of Ayurveda) containing descriptions about several medicinal plants. There are several books dealing with formulation and pharmaceuticals too. Description of several minerals useful in skin care had been registered from the ancient Indian Astrochemical books, description of all of them is beyond the scope of any single review hence further research and review work is welcomed in this particular field.

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